

AN OVERVIEW OF CONSTRUCTION ENGINEERING SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT:

Construction industry is one of the fastest growing compared to other industries. The development of any country basically needs an infrastructure which could sustain for long time. The infrastructure development leads to the development of the construction engineering. In the construction industries, now days the management has played the vital role for completion of the project during specified time and with minimum possible losses. The construction management has become very popular and has opened new doors of the opportunities for the management students all over the world. The construction industries are passing through the transition phase. Previously most of the systems were human dependent but now the processes are simplified with the help of the technology. Authors have tried to present an overview of the scenario of construction industries over the recent years and also discussed the upcoming technologies in the field of the construction industries.

KEYWORDS: Construction, management, planning, opportunities in construction management, etc.

INTRODUCTION:

The contribution of the construction industry in India's GDP is around 8 percent which is increasing as the construction industries are increasing. The construction industry has not only the revenue generation from the infrastructure development but also from the manufacturing of the raw material required for the construction. The modern construction industries are required to use the modern equipments required for the construction. The following table shows the turnover of the construction industry over past few years and it has observed that the industry has remarkable support to the India's GDP.

Table 1: Gross value added yearly in construction industry

Sr. No	Year	Gross value added Rs. In Crore
1	2011-12	777,363
2	2012-13	847,492
3	2013-14	919,269
4	2014-15	977,992
5	2015-16	1,000,459
6	2016-17	1,064,068
7	%	7.74 %

The GDP of any country is measure of the development in the country. The construction industries were sharing the remarkable percentage of GDP in India and also in many other countries. The GDP from the construction in India is around 2200 Indian Billion Rs in fourth quarter of 2016.

Fig. No. 1: India's GDP from construction in year 2016

Fig. No. 2: USA's GDP from construction in year 2016

Fig. No. 3: India's GDP from construction in year 2016

Fig. No. 4: China's GDP from construction in year 2016

Fig. No. 5: France's GDP from construction in year 2016

Fig. No. 6: Australia's GDP from construction in year 2016

The few of the construction equipments used over last few years are as below:

Fig. No. 7: Earthmoving machinery

Fig. No. 8: Material Mixing Machine

Previously the problem faced with the construction industry is failure in timely delivery and completion of the project. The construction industry was always criticized due to the failure of the timely completion. The less availability of workers, failure of the planning, failure of availability of the raw material was the causes of the above stated problem and hence the management of the construction is necessary.

CONCLUSION:

Authors have presented the review of the scenario of the construction industry over last one year for different countries and it is observed that the industry has contributed remarkably in the GDP of most of the countries. The industrial growth needs the better infrastructure and it's the responsibility of a construction industry to develop a sustainable infrastructure. The contribution of construction industry is increasing year by year. The main construction and other supporting industries have opened new doors for many workers seeking job. The industry has great future ahead with the implementation of technology for better structures.

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